

**COGNITIVE UNITS OF LANGUAGE AS AN OBJECT OF RESEARCH IN
INTERDISCIPLINARY SCIENCES**

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ABSTRACT. This article discusses the issue of cognitive units of the language, about the research of this discipline in the fields of interdisciplinary sciences. This article examines the question of how and how cognitive linguistics appeared, what it has in common and different with other disciplines, and how important it plays in the modern Russian language.

KEY WORDS: verbal expressions, conscious words, language, communication, language system, semantics, Cognitive linguistics, concept, language structures, cognition, category.

INTRODUCTION: Language is one of the main attributes of a person, the principle of "individual formation". Undoubtedly, it is with the appearance of conscious words, verbal expressions, together with physical labor, that is a powerful means of developing a person, his consciousness and the whole society, the formation of a person as a rational being begins. The early stage of human development is associated with the emergence of labor, the formation of consciousness and self-awareness of a person as a member of a certain collective. Only with the development of language as a signaling system, it can transmit information about the surrounding reality, allowing people to speak abstractly, based on specific objects and situations, and think abstractly, which not only provides opportunities for communication between specific members of the collective, it also creates conditions for social experience.

Human society not only revives language, but also activates the language system. However, we cannot describe language one way or another without taking into account the cognitive process.

Cognitive science itself, under the auspices of which cognitive linguistics appeared, is increasingly divided not only into different schools, but also into various cognitive sciences, among which are cognitive psychology, neuroscience, anthropology, etc. Various scientists give their own interpretation of the term cognitive, depending on which particular science it is used in. Cognitive linguistics, on the one hand, considering language as a cognitive process that allows explanations about any objects in the form of a verbalized description of them, on the other hand, pays great attention to the issues of semantics, which, being a link between the theory of language and theories of other cognitive abilities, can in no way be separated from cognition. R. Jakobson considers a person as a certain existing level of mental representation, at which linguistic information is combined with sensory: sensory or motor. He calls this level a conceptual structure, considering it in parallel with the semantic structure. The formation of the conceptual structure is carried out with the help of basic conceptual categories, or "semantic parts of speech", such as an Object, an Event State, Action, etc. The listed basic categories can be expanded into more complex expressions according to certain rules.

If we consider this category from the point of view of E.S. Kubryakova, then, in her opinion, "the paradoxical position lies in the fact that in this series verbal memory is opposed to all other types of memory - figurative, motor, sensory, which is right and wrong equally. That's right, because, in all likelihood, all sensory types of memory each have their own "traces". It is wrong, because according to our deep conviction, verbal or linguistic memory itself organizes the same elements of sensory, figurative and motor memory into a single system of verbal anagrams,

where these elements are already connected with language, the verbal form of their existence.”

If we compare cognitive linguistics with other disciplines of the cognitive cycle, then this discipline is primarily interested only in those cognitions that are inherent in a person: that is, mental mechanisms of understanding and generating speech that are associated with the representation of language knowledge as a special mechanism for processing or processing information. In this regard, the main task of cognitive linguistics is to define a systematic description and explanation of the mechanisms of human language acquisition and the principles of structuring these mechanisms.

To solve this problem, it is important for us to understand the content and outline the boundaries of the concept of cognition as a whole. If we take the development of cognitivism at the turn of the present time, then this concept has significantly expanded its scope: such concepts as knowledge, consciousness, reason, thinking, representation, creativity, development of a speech thinking strategy, symbolization, logical inference, fantasy and many other cognitions are summed up under it. Cognition is, at this stage of the development of linguistics, the basic concept of cognitive linguistics, provides it with broader horizons than those available to the traditional theory of the relationship between language and thinking. In cognitive linguistics, knowledge and opinions are considered from the point of view of their representation by language structures.

Thus, cognitive linguistics is one of the new cognitive sciences, the object of research of which is the nature and essence of knowledge and cognition, the results of perception of reality and cognitive activity of a person accumulated in the form of meaningful and brought into a certain system of information.

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